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Los factores de personalidad de los docentes en la gestión de conflictos en el aula

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Resumen

El estudio tuvo como objetivo comprender el impacto predictivo de los cinco factores de la personalidad de los docentes (neuroticismo, extroversión, apertura a la experiencia, amabilidad y responsabilidad), en el manejo de conflictos en el aula. También se estudiaron las variables género, tiempo de servicio y formación académica de los docentes cuando se relacionaron con dimensiones de personalidad. Se utilizaron como instrumentos el NEO-Inventario de Cinco Factores, el Inventario de Conflicto Organizacional de Rahim-II - Versión Portuguesa en el Contexto Escolar y una ficha de datos personales y profesionales, en una muestra de 659 profesores de educación básica en escuelas portuguesas. Utilizando un modelo de ecuaciones estructurales, los resultados mostraron una asociación entre todas las variables en estudio. El neuroticismo y la responsabilidad son los mejores predictores de la gestión de conflictos. El género femenino es el que presenta mejores resultados en todas las dimensiones de la personalidad. Los docentes con mayor formación académica mostraron menos neuroticismo, pero eran más extrovertidos, abiertos a la experiencia, agradables y responsables, y los de mayor antigüedad mostraron menos neuroticismo, extraversión, apertura a la experiencia y amabilidad. Estos resultados constituirán un motor movilizador de prácticas pedagógicas más sustantivas para el avance de la educación.

Palabras clave

Personalidad; gestión de conflictos; maestros; aula.

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The teachers' personality factors on classroom conflict management

Abstract

The study aimed to understand the predictive impact of the five factors of teachers' personalities (neuroticism, extroversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and responsibility) on conflict management in the classroom. The variables of gender, service time and academic training of teachers were also studied when they were related to personality dimensions. The NEO-Five Factors Inventory, the Rahim-II Organizational Conflict Inventory - Portuguese Version in the School Context, and a personal and professional data sheet were used as instruments, in a sample of 659 basic education teachers in Portuguese schools. Using a structural equation model, the results showed an association between all the variables under study. Neuroticism and responsibility are the best predictors of conflict management. The female gender is the one that presents the best results in all dimensions of personality. Teachers with more academic training showed less neuroticism, but were more extroverted, open to experience, agreeable, and responsible, and those with more seniority showed less neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, and agreeable. These results will constitute a mobilizing engine of more substantive pedagogical practices for the advancement of education.

Key words

Personality; conflict management; teachers; classroom.

Introduction

From the literature review on studies alluding to conflict management, it is observable the growing importance that has been dedicated to this theme due to social visibility, more specifically, having students as the target population. In this study, however, the focus is on the teacher as a professional who, in his daily practice, is faced with different situations of indiscipline, thus requiring a great capacity to manage conflicts.

Considering this individual focus on the teacher, Baykal (2019) mentions that the personal characteristics of individuals contribute to a climate of conflict management, influence the way they interpret the conflict experienced, and play an important role in explaining the process associated with its management and, predictably in its outcome. The author also mentions that the expansion of studies that seek to relate personality factors with the behavior of subjects in conflict management is clear, thus justifying the study of the association between these two constructs.

Intrinsic to the human being, conflict with others, with oneself, and with the institution is at the heart of the educational relationship (Pérez-de-Guzmán et al., 2011), whose causes are due to personality, differences in culture, values, needs, interests, and power (Almost et al., 2016), and the school is a context where there is a significant amount of conflict.

Thus, school conflict is defined as the disagreement between individuals or groups about ideas, interests, principles, and values within the school community, where the parties

involved understand their interests as excluded (Pérez-Serrano et al., 2011), and the most frequent conflicts occur between students and between them and teachers (Santamaría-Villar, et al., 2021). For Rabidjanovna et al. (2021) the conflict in the teacher-student(s) relationship is characterized by a set of attitudes that include a wide range of negative student behaviors, such as lack of participation during classes, disturbing colleagues and the class itself, and situations of verbal (e.g., insulting colleagues) or physical (e.g., destruction of school facilities and equipment, personal objects of colleagues).

Therefore, teaching activity requires a great capacity for interpersonal relationships and effective conflict management (Valente & Lourenço, 2020; 2022), where the use of attitudes and behaviors more appropriate to the situation is of extreme relevance in the day-to-day lives of all those involved in the educational context. Then, the personal characteristics of individuals contribute to the creation of a climate of conflictual management, influence how the subjects interpret the conflict experienced, and play a fundamental role in explaining the process associated with its management and, predictably, its outcome. It is clear the expansion of studies that seek to relate the personality factors with the subjects' behaviors in conflict management (Baykal, 2019).

It is worth highlighting the justification of Delatorre et al. (2021) when they mention that personality has an influence on the conflict management procedure, namely in terms of the possible relationship between certain personality traits and the motivations that originate a conflict, in attitudes and behaviors developed during the conflict situation and in the way individuals interpret their experience.

In this way, one of the themes that have aroused the most interest in the research, concerning the behavior of individuals in conflict, has been the study of personality characteristics (Cunha et al., 2016), as they contribute to establishing the nature of the conflict management process (Martins et al., 2016) and help in understanding the behaviors developed in conflict situations (Delatorre et al., 2021). The emergence of the Big Five model, by Costa et al. (1992), allowed the creation of a specific taxonomy on the different variables and personality traits, allowing a greater understanding of these variables in other constructs (Hopwood et al. (2022).

The personality and its dimensions

Although there are various definitions of personality, most have three main aspects: the uniqueness of the individual and what distinguishes him from all others; a set of stable and lasting characteristics, over time and situations; and the characteristic style of connection/interaction between the subject and the physical and social environment (Möttus et al., 2017). The different definitions have the essential characteristic that personality is a personal construction that occurs in the course of life. This cannot be separated from personal aspects, such as the emotional, intellectual, physiological, and socio-moral sphere, and it does not exist, also, free of the conscience and self-representation, that each one has, nor of their self-esteem (Bergner, 2020).

The most recent definitions of personality have been valuing the interactive and dynamic components, proving the perspective of Piovesan et al. (2018) who understand personality as a system delimited by personality traits and dynamic processes that intervene in the individual psychological process, and one of the approaches with the greatest empirical support is Big Five Model (McCrae et al., 2004). However, McLean et al., (2021)

states that individuals are characterized by their patterns of thoughts, feelings, and actions, and involve a dimensional representation of interpersonal differences at the level of personality whose validity, understanding, universality, and longitudinal stability have been repeatedly underlined by empirical research. This model brings together the behavioral, emotional, and cognitive tendencies of individuals in five major categories or dimensions (McCrae et al., 2004): Neuroticism; Extroversion; Openness to experience; Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness.

Thus, we started this study motivated by the conviction that personality traits are strong predictors of academic and professional performance, which has been corroborated throughout the literature review (Brandt et al., 2019; Luan et al., 2017; Stajkovic et al., 2018).

The first dimension, neuroticism, is characterized by the propensity to experience negative effects (sadness, fear, anger, guilt, embarrassment), and is associated with emotional instability. It is related to the management of emotions, translated into vulnerability and anxiety, being relevant for the study of the perception of social support, since the management of emotions is essential for the development of interpersonal relationships. Individuals with high levels of neuroticism are characterized as more unstable, insecure, and prone to psychological distress and, eventually, may have higher levels of anxiety, depression, hostility, vulnerability, self-criticism, and impulsivity (Costa et al., 2008).

The second dimension, extroversion, associated with a state of sociability, is related to characteristics such as interpersonal assertiveness, confidence, and creativity, that is, it refers to empathetic, persistent, optimistic, active, affable individuals who value socialization (Bertoquini et al., 2006). The concept of extraversion predicts individual impact levels in group interaction, where individuals with good levels of extraversion tend towards interpersonal development, relationship building, social skills, and the desire to work in partnership (Barry et al., 1998).

The third dimension, openness to experience, is related to imagination, curiosity, originality, open-mindedness, and diverse and non-traditional interests. It involves a proactive intellectual activity, high cultural orientation, creativity, imagination, and preference for tasks that involve cognitive complexity (McCrae et al., 1997). Openness to experience seems to be one of the domains with the greatest congruence between partners, being associated with the longevity and stability of the relationship, as it is also related to more effective emotional regulation strategies between individuals (Rammstedt et al., 2013).

Agreeableness is the fourth dimension and is characterized as an indicator of high sympathy, flexibility, trust, tolerance, and a denounced orientation towards helpfulness and cooperation, caring for others (Costa et al., 1992). Individuals with a higher level of kindness are able to regulate themselves emotionally during interpersonal relationships (Graziano et al., 1997). However, individuals with a low propensity for kindness are often apprehensive, skeptical, and competitive.

Finally, the fifth dimension called conscientiousness reflects discernment, organization, a sense of responsibility, self-discipline, persistence, prudence, and the ability to plan behaviors (Costa et al., 2001). According to McCrae et al. (2008), conscientiousness can be expressed in honesty and evaluates performance, motivation, organization, and persistence toward a goal to be achieved, but it can also be associated with greater self-control and a lower level of aggressive outsourcing. According to the authors, individuals

with high values of conscientiousness have high levels of perseverance, reduced impulsiveness, and a strong tendency towards personal achievement, in addition to being responsible about work and the tasks under their responsibility. It sometimes appears associated with an attitude of concern for their interests.

In addition to the differences found in terms of gender, the literature indicates that there are not only differences at an emotional level (higher levels of anxiety and nervousness in women), but also a social expectation related to congruent behavior with friendlier traits centered on the female gender. (Costa et al., 2001; Jaušovec et al., 2007). Other studies indicate the existence of small variations in the effect of the female gender on neuroticism, conscientiousness and agreeableness (Cyniak-Cieciura, et al., 2021). Regarding academic training, Hojat et al. (2004) highlight the importance of the association between academic qualifications and personality, as having higher education has a positive effect on personality scores (Magalhães et al., 2014). As for the relationship between service time and the personality of individuals, the relationships are associated with their psychosocial maturity (McCrae et al., 1999).

Personality versus conflict management

In this sequence, it is possible to argue about the influence of personality dimensions in conflict management. For example, neuroticism is associated with higher levels of aggressive externalization and less self-control, resulting in a more negative view of the conflict, leading to less effective emotion regulation strategies (Schroder-Abé et al., 2015). As they are associated with stress, anxiety, and anguish factors, they may predict a lower ability to deal with possible rejections of any kind. Individuals with a neurotic tendency are likely to perceive conflict as a threat, expressing a strong need to avoid any conflict or act too passionately (Cyniak-Cieciura et al., 2021).

In turn, extroverted individuals are usually associated with a greater willingness to accept the opinion of others, which could facilitate any conflict management situation. Lawrence (2015) states that extroverted individuals tend to influence others to resolve conflicts in their favor, and rarely resort to situations of distancing themselves from the problem.

It should be noted that the emotional regulation of teachers enables effective management of discipline in the classroom (Valente et al., 2020a). Individuals with a high level of openness to experience are more likely to choose attitudes and behaviors based on flexibility and adaptability in conflict management, showing consideration for the other's point of view (Moberg, 2001).

For Jensen-Campbell et al. (2001), kindness is the aspect associated with interpersonal relationships and the motivation to establish positive interpersonal relationships. Kindness assumes special importance in the social context and in situations of conflict, where cooperation and consideration for the results of others are relevant aspects, facilitating the management of conflicts, and mitigating their occurrence (McCrae et al., 2005). In turn, conscientious individuals can enter into conflict management dynamics where they opt for more integrative behaviors or simply compete for their interests (McLean et al., 2021). Thus, it is expected to find a negative relationship between neuroticism and conflict management (Lima, 1997) and positive relationships with extroversion, openness to experience, kindness, and conscientiousness (Lourenço et al., 2004).

Study purpose

Returning to what was previously explained by Baykal (2019), regarding the importance of individuals' personal characteristics and the need to carry out studies that relate personality factors to individuals' behaviors in conflict management, this study aims to understand the predictive impact of the five factors of teachers' personalities (neuroticism, extroversion, openness to experience, kindness, and conscientiousness) in the management of conflicts in the classroom.

Based on the literature review, the following hypotheses are presented: Hypothesis 1) A positive and statistically significant influence is expected between the female gender and the dimensions of the personality neuroticism, extroversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness; Hypothesis 2) A positive and statistically significant influence is expected between academic training and personality dimensions with the exception of neuroticism; Hypothesis 3: A negative and statistically significant influence is expected between the service time and the dimensions of the personality, with the exception of conscientiousness; Hypothesis 4) Negative and statistically significant influence between neuroticism and conflict management is expected; Hypothesis 5) A positive and statistically significant influence between extroversion and school conflict management is expected; Hypothesis 6) A positive and statistically significant influence between openness to experience and school conflict management is expected; Hypothesis 7) A positive and statistically significant influence between agreeableness and conflict management is expected; and Hypothesis 8) A positive and statistically significant influence between conscientiousness and school conflict management is expected.

Methodology

Sample

A convenience sample consisting of 659 teachers (437 women) working in Portuguese public schools (5th-7th) from the north of Portugal, aged between 32 and 65 years ($M = 49$), was used. Of these, 36 are bachelors, 467 have graduated, 138 hold a master's degree, and 18 have a doctorate. Regarding service time, 58 were less than 10 years old, 121 were between 10 and 20 years old, 318 were between 21 and 30 years old and 162 were over 30 years old.

Instruments

The final questionnaire was formed by the following instruments:

Personal and Professional Data Sheet: to characterize the sample (gender, academic training, service time).

NEO-Five Factor Inventory (NEO-FFI; Magalhães et al., 2014): Consisting of 60 items distributed over five dimensions, with twelve items each, to which Cronbach's alphas are associated, namely: (a) Neuroticism ($\alpha = .89$; e.g., I often arrange discussions with my family and co-workers); (b) Extroversion ($\alpha = .81$; e.g., I love to talk to other people); (c) Openness to experience ($\alpha = .84$; e.g., I often try new and unknown foods); (d) Agreeableness ($\alpha = .87$; e.g., I try to be gentle with everyone I meet) and; (e) Conscientiousness ($\alpha = .84$; e.g., I try conscientiously to fulfill all my obligations). A 5-point Likert-type scale was used, from *strongly disagree* (1) to *strongly agree* (5).

Rahim Organizational Conflict Inventory II - Portuguese Version in School Context (ROCI-II-PViSC; Valente et al., 2017): Consisting of 28 items, distributed over five dimensions, to which the corresponding Cronbach alphas are associated, namely: (a) Integrating, with seven items ($\alpha = .87$; e.g., Faced with difficulty in working with a student, I try to analyze the situation with him to find a solution acceptable to both); (b) Obliging, with six items ($\alpha = .75$; e.g., Facing a work problem, I usually try to satisfy my student's needs); (c) Dominating, with five items ($\alpha = .83$; e.g., Faced with a problematic situation with a student, I generally show myself to try to impose my point of view); (d) Avoiding, with six items ($\alpha = .75$; e.g., I try not to show disagreement with students) and; (e) Compromising, with four items ($\alpha = .81$; e.g., Facing work problems, I try to reach agreements with my students). A 5-point Likert-type scale was used, from *totally disagree* (1) to *totally agree* (5).

Procedures

After obtaining the authorization of the General Directorate of Education and the Directors of the schools, the instruments were applied, in 2021, in a school context. Conventional ethical and deontological procedures were guaranteed, namely the confidentiality of responses and voluntary participation.

Data analysis

The data were analyzed using the SPSS/AMOS 25 program, using the maximum likelihood estimation method (ML; Arbuckle, 2016). All cases with missing values were eliminated and the outliers were kept moderate since the sample's descriptive statistics were still adequate.

The metric characteristics of the items were also considered as a function of the means, standard deviations, and indicators of asymmetry and kurtosis. To assess the normality of the sample distribution, it was considered as a criterion that asymmetry values greater than two and kurtosis value greater than seven should not be considered (Finney & DiStefano, 2013).

Subsequently, in order to analyze the model, the structural equation models technique was used (SEM; Lowe et al., 2007). The adjustment of the model under study was estimated considering the statistical indexes most used in international research and the respective cutoff points, namely: GFI and AGFI $\geq .90$; TPI $\geq .95$; TLI $\geq .95$; RMSEA $< .05$, according Marôco (2018); and CN: $r > 200$ (Hoelter, 1983). The specific influence of personality factors on the dimensions of conflict management was assessed according: less than .20 is insignificant; between .20 and .50, small; between .50 and .80 is moderate; and greater than .80, large (Ferguson, 2009). Later, the variability of the conflict management explained by the personality factor was reported by η^2 : less than .04 is insignificant, between .04 and .25, small, between .25 and .64 moderate, and greater than .64, great (Ferguson, 2009).

Results

Table 1 presents the descriptive data (mean, standard deviation, asymmetry, and kurtosis) corresponding to the variables considered in the study. Consciousness ($M = 43.54$) and neuroticism ($M = 41.39$) were the dimensions that obtained more robust averages, followed by openness to experience ($M = 40.32$). The SEM presents the variables and respective study hypotheses (c.f. Figure 1).

Table 1

Descriptive statistics

Variables	Min.	Máx.	Mean	D.P.	Asymmetry	Kurtosis
Neuroticism	12	60	41.39	13.791	-.086	-1.029
Extroversion	12	60	39.98	9.638	.204	1.323
Openness to experience	12	60	40.32	10.941	.247	.231
Agreeableness	12	60	37.64	12.655	-.074	.015
Conscientiousness	12	60	43.54	9.848	-.506	1.124
Classroom conflict management	73	133	98.64	10.978	.466	-.072

The results showed the following adjustment indices: $\chi^2 (13) = 17,613$; $p = .173$; $\chi^2 / g.l. = 1,355$; $GFI = .994$; $AGFI = .980$; $CFI = .989$; $TLI = .969$; $RMSEA = .023$ (LO/.000 - HI/.048). The values reached in the goodness indexes suggested that the global adjustment of the multiple linear regression model could be considered as good and confirmed the relationships between the variables existing in the empirical matrix. The values of the Hoelter index were also adjusted [CN = 836 (0.05) and 1,035 (0.01)], attesting to the adequacy of the sample size of the model. The parameters found in the model revealed appropriate and statistically significant values.

Figure 1. Model under study (n = 659)

From the analysis of Figure 1, it is ensured that the hypotheses that guided the specifications were confirmed and the existing relationships between the variables are statistically significant, although part of the values obtained is low. Thus, teachers who claim to be more prone to neuroticism showed a tendency to be less effective in classroom conflict management ($\beta = -0.211$; $p < .001$). On the other hand, those who presented higher values in extroversion ($\beta = 0.134$; $p < .001$), openness to experience ($\beta = 0.127$; $p < .01$), agreeableness ($\beta = 0.109$; $p < .01$), and conscientiousness ($\beta = 0.136$; $p < .001$), showed a tendency to be more efficient in classroom conflict management.

Regarding the personal and professional variables, it was found that the female gender had better results in all dimensions of personality, that is, she presented positive and statistically significant relationships with neuroticism ($\beta = 0.137$; $p < .001$), extroversion ($\beta = 0.127$; $p < .01$), openness to experience ($\beta = 0.113$; $p < .01$), agreeableness ($\beta = .214$; $p < .001$), and conscientiousness ($\beta = 0.157$; $p < .001$).

In academic training, teachers who had a higher academic level exhibited less neuroticism ($\beta = -0.125$; $p < .001$), however, they demonstrated to have more extroversion ($\beta = 0.127$; $p < .01$), open to experience ($\beta = 0.117$; $p < .01$), agreeableness ($\beta = 0.112$; $p < .01$), and conscientiousness ($\beta = 0.110$; $p < .01$).

Teachers who had more service time showed less neuroticism ($\beta = -0.419$; $p < .001$), extraversion ($\beta = -0.124$; $p < .01$), openness to experience ($\beta = -0.153$; $p < .001$), and agreeableness ($\beta = -0.107$; $p < .001$), however, are more conscientious ($\beta = 0.120$; $p < .01$). It should be noted that all the relationships that make up the model are statistically significant.

With regard to multiple square correlations, these indicated that conflict management in the classroom is explained by personality factors and exogenous variables (gender, academic training, service time) in about 11% ($\eta^2 = .105$). In turn, the personality dimension that is best explained by exogenous variables is neuroticism with a value of 20% ($\eta^2 = .201$), followed by agreeableness with 7% ($\eta^2 = .071$), openness to experience 6% ($\eta^2 = .057$), extroversion 5% ($\eta^2 = .052$), and conscientiousness with 4% ($\eta^2 = .036$).

Discussion

It has been proven that gender, academic training, and service time for teachers are related to each of the personality dimensions, although the values obtained are low. Even so, all the relationships are statistically significant.

Regarding gender differences, it is observed that women scored significantly more on agreeableness, conscientiousness, and neuroticism followed by extraversion and openness to experience, proving Hypothesis 1, in which a positive and statistically significant relationship between the female gender was expected and the dimensions of the personality. The differences found between gender and personality dimensions are plausible since it seems to be clear in the literature (Costa et al., 2001) that there are not only gender differences at the emotional level (higher levels of anxiety and nervousness in women).

Other studies also reveal the existence of small variations in the effect of the female gender on neuroticism, conscientiousness, and agreeableness (Colliver, 2007). This result is theoretically congruent, as the literature suggests that there are some psychosocial gender specificities, particularly, the greater investment of women in attendance, reflecting more

pleasantness. Studies carried out state that women tend to have higher values of neuroticism when compared to men (Costa et al., 2001; Jaušovec et al., 2007).

Academic training relates to all dimensions of personality, except for neuroticism, confirming Hypothesis 2. The results are in agreement with the Hojat and Xu (2004) study, since having higher education studies may be associated with evidence that supports the importance of personality factors in predicting socially valued behaviors and in recognizing personality as a component of an individual's willingness to perform (Roberts et al., 2007).

Thus, it appears that the subjects with more academic training tend to have higher scores in the opening to experience, reflecting the willingness of these individuals to stimulate experiences and seek knowledge. This result is to be expected since in its conceptual definition this is the only factor that is associated with creativity, which is a dimension of intelligence. Individuals who score highly in opening up to experience tend to actively seek knowledge and, this fact may be preferentially stimulated or reinforced at higher levels of education. On the other hand, those who are open to experience will find it easier to progress academically as they tend to have greater creativity/intelligence (Chamorro-Premuzic et al., 2006). Likewise, subjects who have more academic training tend to be more prone to extroversion, agreeableness, and conscientiousness.

The negative relationship between academic training and neuroticism can be explained by the fact that teachers, having more academic knowledge and greater awareness of reflective praxis, demonstrate greater anxiety and dissatisfaction with the results of their work and, thus, externalize greater levels of vulnerability, emotional insecurity, and anxiety, characteristics of neuroticism that are essential when making decisions.

The service time is negatively related to all personality factors, except conscientiousness, these relationships being statistically significant, confirming Hypothesis 3. Negative relationships may be associated with greater awareness of the strengths and weaknesses of your performance in their functions related to your psychosocial maturity (McCrae et al. 1999a). On the other hand, the positive relationship with conscientiousness can be explained by the fact that teachers with more professional experience are more confident and are more aware of the importance and need to promote collaborative work, systematically, in favor of constructive conflict management in the classroom.

Regarding neuroticism, the results demonstrate the existence of a negative and statistically significant association with classroom conflict management, having been the factor with the greatest explanatory contribution, although of low magnitude, proving Hypothesis 4. This result can be justified by the fact that teachers with higher levels of neuroticism reveal less effective emotional regulation strategies, due to the greater tendency to manage their emotions inappropriately (Schroder-Abé et al., 2015) and, thus, show less capacity in the management of conflict situations. In this study, neuroticism was the personality factor that revealed the most robust mean value, which is congruent with international research (Magalhães et al., 2014). In this sense, Ayachit et al., (2014) emphasizes that conflicts stimulate negative feelings and that their management consists of a demanding cognitive task. As such, individuals with a neurotic tendency are likely to perceive conflict as a threat and, thus, express a strong need to avoid any conflict or act in a very passionate way (Cyniak-Cieciura, et al., 2021).

Neuroticism when integrating different personality traits, namely vulnerability, psychosocial maladjustment, and anxiety, may explain the fact that teachers with high scores on this factor have difficulty in managing conflicts. As mentioned by Costa and McCrae (2008) individuals with high values of neuroticism are less able to control impulses and stressful situations, as well as tend to experience conflicts as threatening situations, trying to avoid conflict or confront the same by helping themselves with more competitive strategies. All of these factors associated with neuroticism may contribute to ineffective conflict management by teachers.

Regarding extroversion, the results indicate that the most extroverted teachers tend to better manage conflict situations in the classroom, confirming Hypothesis 5. Extroverted individuals are usually characterized as sociable and emotionally positive (Lawrence, 2015) thus being more qualified teachers for conflict management. They are characterized by an energetic style of interpersonal approach and a strong inclination toward the establishment of relationships, social skills, and the desire to work with others (John et al., 2008), essential characteristics of conflict management in the classroom.

These teachers are more willing to accept students' opinions, which facilitates classroom conflict management. As extroverted individuals show a tendency to influence others to resolve conflicts, rarely resorting to situations of withdrawal from the problem (Lawrence, 2015).

As for the openness to experience, the results reveal a positive and significant impact on the way teachers manage conflict, confirming Hypothesis 6. This dimension of personality is associated with more effective strategies for emotional regulation among individuals (Rammstedt et al., 2013), which enables effective management of the discipline in the classroom (Valente et al., 2020a).

Teachers with great openness to experience choose to be guided by more collaborative and committed behaviors. Individuals who score highly in opening up to experience are more susceptible to choosing attitudes and behaviors based on flexibility and adaptability in conflict management, expressing consideration from the other's point of view (Moberg, 2001).

Concerning agreeableness, this factor is characterized as an indicator of high sympathy, flexibility, trust, and cooperation (Costa et al., 1992). The results of this study indicate that teachers who score more in the agreeableness dimension have a greater capacity for conflict management, that is, they are more collaborative in the face of a conflict in the classroom and manage it more efficiently, this relationship being statistically significant, confirming Hypothesis 7. As agreeableness is related to the establishment of positive interpersonal relationships (Jensen-Campbell et al., 2001), it assumes special classroom importance faces a conflict in the teacher-student(s) relationship, proving the relationship is positive and statistically significant between these variables.

Regarding conscientiousness, the results indicate a positive and statistically significant relationship with conflict management, confirming Hypothesis 8. Conscientiousness is associated with attitudes and behaviors that facilitate the satisfaction of the interests of both parties, and related greater self-control and a lower level of aggressive externalization explain the results obtained. In this sequence, a teacher who

tends to be more conscientious has a greater capacity to manage a conflict situation that develops in the classroom.

It should be noted that the initial theoretical rationale regarding personality scales indicates the stability of this construct in adulthood. Although adverse life events do not seem to have an impact on the personality of individuals, however, the literature review indicates that there are changes in the five factors at different times in the life cycle. In other words, an increase in conscientiousness and kindness is observed over time, while extroversion and neuroticism, and openness to experience tend to decrease (Martin et al., 2006).

Although the values obtained are fragile, this does not mean that the proposed model is inadequate to describe the relationships between the variables under study but rather incomplete to describe the complexity that involves the two constructs. The data suggest the need, in future investigations, for the model to include some mediating variables that may increase the understanding of this process and eventually justify the low explained variance of the model. Variables such as the perception of the teacher's self-efficacy and emotional intelligence may be some of the important dimensions that would contribute to a more holistic view of this area of study.

As for the limitations, the first obstacle was related to the fact that the sample used is limited to the northern part of the country, needs to be expanded numerically and geographically, as well as must include teachers from other levels of education. Another limitation is related to the application of self-report questionnaires in the evaluation of the variables under analysis, using a convenience sample, which may condition the analysis and interpretation of the results and their generalization. Nevertheless, these data reinforce the potential of the scales used, since the results obtained are consistent with what was expected from the theoretical point of view.

Conclusion

This study aimed to explore the contribution of personality factors to conflict management in the classroom. An attempt was also made to identify the impact of gender, academic training, and length of service on each of the personality factors. The results were found to present an important contribution to the educational panorama. This finding becomes more relevant if we consider that the studies that associate these two constructs are scarce and that the results are not sufficiently congruent, thus reducing the possibility of comparing the values obtained, so it is important to continue to research this area.

Finally, the progressive realization of studies with these constructs will allow the collection of robust empirical evidence that facilitates the understanding of all the processes that are underlying the perception of the influence of the factors on the personality of the teachers. These will constitute a mobilizing engine of more substantive pedagogical practices for the advancement of education, contributing to the promotion and specialization of conflict management in an educational context and to the quality of the teaching and learning process.

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